

VARIABLE DYNAMIC MODE DECOMPOSITION FOR ESTIMATING TIME EIGENVALUES IN NUCLEAR SYSTEMS

Ethan Smith, Ilham Variansyah, and Ryan G. McClarren

Department of Aerospace and Mechanical Engineering
University of Notre Dame
Notre Dame, Indiana USA
{esmith45, ijuanda, rmcclarr}@nd.edu

ABSTRACT

An extension to the Dynamic Mode Decomposition method for calculating time eigenvalues (also known as α eigenvalues) that removes the requirement of a constant time step is derived and demonstrated. The new method, called variable-dynamic mode decomposition (V-DMD), is shown to be accurate when computing eigenvalues for systems that were infeasible with DMD due to a large separation in time scales. The alpha eigenvalues of an infinite medium neutron transport problem with delayed neutrons and consequently having multiple, very different relevant time scales are computed. Furthermore, V-DMD is shown to be of similar accuracy to the original DMD approach when computing eigenvalues in other systems where DMD can be used.

KEYWORDS: time eigenvalues, data-driven algorithms, time-dependent neutronics

1. INTRODUCTION

Time eigenvalues [1], also known as α eigenvalues, are important for understanding the dynamics of the neutron population in a system. This eigenvalue problem is more challenging than the more well-known k eigenvalue problem because time eigenvalues have the angular flux as the eigenvector, rather than the scalar flux eigenvectors in k calculations.

The typical $k - \alpha$ iteration procedure [2,3] for finding these eigenvalues is ill-suited for many subcritical problems because the iteration procedure can introduce total cross-sections that are effectively negative. Furthermore, most methods for estimating time eigenvalues can only calculate the eigenvalue farthest to the right in the complex plane, even though in a subcritical experiment this mode may not be important.

The dynamic mode decomposition (DMD) has recently been introduced to the neutron transport community for the purpose of estimating time eigenvalues in calculations [4] and experiments [5], as well as to create reduced-order models [6], improve the convergence of power iteration in k -eigenvalue problems [7], and to accelerate source iteration [8,9]. Originally introduced for computational fluid dynamics problems, this method relies on taking the solution to a time-dependent transport problem and using the solution at several time steps to estimate the transport operator based solely on the available solutions. This approximate operator has eigenvalue-eigenvector pairs that are also eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the full transport operator. Because DMD is a fully data-driven method, it finds the eigenmodes that are important in the system's evolution. Furthermore, the approximate operator that DMD estimates can be used to evolve the system forward in time.

One drawback of DMD is that it requires the solution data to be at equally spaced time intervals. This drawback is significant for transport problems with delayed neutrons as we will demonstrate. It would be

better to allow the time step to increase after the initial prompt transients decay away. Such a variable time step, perhaps logarithmically spaced, would be more efficient.

In this paper, we present a dynamic mode decomposition method that allows for variable time steps that we call variable dynamic mode decomposition V-DMD. This method changes the DMD procedure to allow for variable time steps, but does need to know the type of time discretization used in producing the solution. In the following section we present the method and then show how it can be used on a variety of problems.

2. THEORY OF A VARIABLE STEP DECOMPOSITION

We extend the DMD procedure to accept a variable time step for determining α eigenvalues by leveraging the fact that we know which time discretization method was used to create the data matrix. We begin with a generic, linear system of differential equations of the form

$$\frac{d}{dt}\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{y}(t), \quad (1)$$

with initial conditions $\mathbf{y}(0) = \mathbf{y}^0$. The vector \mathbf{y} is of length M , and the matrix \mathbf{A} is of size $M \times M$. In our application \mathbf{A} represents a discretized transport operator, but for most neutron transport calculations this matrix is never explicitly formed. The vector \mathbf{y} contains the spatial, angular, and energy degrees of freedom in the solution.

For the problems presented in this paper we have used the backward Euler method, which conveniently relates our matrix operator A and sequential data vectors \mathbf{y}^n and \mathbf{y}^{n+1} via

$$\frac{\mathbf{y}^{n+1} - \mathbf{y}^n}{t^{n+1} - t^n} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{y}^{n+1}, \quad (2)$$

where the superscripts denote a time level and t^n is the time at the beginning of the n th step.

For N time steps we can rewrite Eq. (2) as

$$\mathbf{Y}^+ = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{Y}^-. \quad (3)$$

Here the matrix \mathbf{Y}^+ is the matrix of size $M \times N$ given by

$$\mathbf{Y}^+ = \left[\left(\frac{\mathbf{y}^N - \mathbf{y}^{N-1}}{t^N - t^{N-1}} \right), \left(\frac{\mathbf{y}^{N-1} - \mathbf{y}^{N-2}}{t^{N-1} - t^{N-2}} \right), \dots, \left(\frac{\mathbf{y}^1 - \mathbf{y}^0}{t^1 - t^0} \right) \right], \quad (4)$$

the matrix \mathbf{Y}^- is given by

$$\mathbf{Y}^- = [y^N, y^{N-1}, \dots, y^1]. \quad (5)$$

Equation (3) looks like the standard setting for DMD, except now the time step size information is contained in the \mathbf{Y}^+ matrix. This allows the operator \mathbf{A} to be approximated using solutions collected at non-equally spaced times.

Following the DMD procedure we take the thin singular-value decomposition (SVD) of the matrix \mathbf{Y}_- :

$$\mathbf{Y}_- = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^*, \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{U} is an $M \times N$ unitary matrix, \mathbf{V} is a $N \times N$ unitary matrix, and $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is an $N \times N$ diagonal matrix with non-negative elements. The asterisk denotes the conjugate-transpose of a matrix. Typically, some of

the diagonal elements of Σ are effectively zero. Therefore, we make Σ the $r \times r$ matrix that contains all r values with magnitude greater than some small, positive ϵ .

With the SVD of \mathbf{Y}^- we right multiply both sides of Eq. (3) by $\mathbf{V}\Sigma^{-1}$, and then left multiply by \mathbf{U}^* to get

$$\mathbf{U}^*\mathbf{Y}^+\mathbf{V}\Sigma^{-1} = \mathbf{U}^*\mathbf{A}\mathbf{U}. \quad (7)$$

The product $\mathbf{U}^*\mathbf{A}\mathbf{U}$ is an $r \times r$ matrix that is approximation to the full operator \mathbf{A} that can be produced *entirely from solution data* as in the LHS of Eq. (7). We call this approximate operator $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{U}^*\mathbf{Y}^+\mathbf{V}\Sigma^{-1}. \quad (8)$$

It can be shown that the eigenvalues of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ are also eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} and that if $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}$ is an eigenvector of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$, then $\mathbf{U}\tilde{\mathbf{v}}$ is an eigenvector of \mathbf{A} .

2.1. V-DMD and Time Eigenvalues for Neutronics

Consider the time-dependent transport equation including delayed neutrons [1]

$$\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t} = \mathcal{A}\psi + \sum_{i=1}^I \frac{\chi_{di}(E)}{4\pi} \lambda_i C_i(x, t), \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} = \int_0^\infty dE \beta_i \nu \Sigma_f(E) \phi(x, E, t) - \lambda_i C_i(x, t), \quad i = 1, \dots, I, \quad (10)$$

where $\psi(x, \Omega, E, t)$ is the angular flux at position $x \in R^3$, in direction $\Omega \in S_2$, at energy E and time t and $C_i(x, t)$ is the delayed precursor density of flavor i . The transport operator \mathcal{A} is given by

$$\mathcal{A} = v(E)(-\Omega \cdot \nabla - \Sigma_t + \mathcal{S} + \mathcal{F}),$$

with \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{F} the scattering and fission operators:

$$\mathcal{S}\psi = \int_{4\pi} d\Omega' \int_0^\infty dE' \Sigma_s(\Omega' \rightarrow \Omega, E' \rightarrow E) \psi(x, \Omega', E', t), \quad (11)$$

$$\mathcal{F}\psi = \frac{\chi_p(E)}{4\pi} \int_0^\infty dE' (1 - \beta) \nu \Sigma_f(E') \phi(x, E', t), \quad (12)$$

where $\Sigma_s(\Omega' \rightarrow \Omega, E' \rightarrow E)$ is the double-differential scattering cross-section from direction Ω' and energy E' to direction Ω and energy E , $\nu \Sigma_f(E')$ is the fission cross-section times the expected number of fission neutrons at energy E' , and $\chi_p(E)$ is the probability of a fission neutron being emitted with energy E , $\chi_{di}(E)$ is the probability of a delayed neutron of flavor i being emitted with energy E , β_i is the fraction of fission neutrons that come from delayed flavor i , $\sum_i \beta_i = \beta$, and λ_i is the decay constant for precursor flavor i . The scalar flux $\phi(x, E, t)$ is defined as the integral of the angular flux over all directions of the unit sphere,

$$\phi(x, E, t) = \int_{4\pi} d\Omega \psi(x, \Omega, E, t). \quad (13)$$

In our study, we will use a discretized transport equation using the multigroup method [1] in energy, discrete ordinates in angle, and a spatial discretization. In this case the time-dependent transport equation can be written as a system of differential equations

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} = \mathbf{A} \Psi(t), \quad (14)$$

where $\Psi(t)$ is a time-dependent vector that includes the delayed neutron precursor densities, and \mathbf{A} is a matrix that represents the discrete transport operator. Notice that the time-eigenvalue problem which supposes a form for $\Psi(t)$ of $e^{\alpha t}\Psi_\alpha$ leads to the eigenvalue problem

$$\alpha\Psi_\alpha = \mathbf{A}\Psi_\alpha. \quad (15)$$

Upon applying the backward Euler discretization to the time derivative in Eq. (14) we get

$$\frac{\Psi^{n+1} - \Psi^n}{t^{n+1} - t^n} = \mathbf{A}\Psi^{n+1}, \quad (16)$$

which is of identical form to Eq. (2).

This suggests the following algorithm for estimating the eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} :

1. Take N backward Euler steps of the discrete transport problem and form the matrices \mathbf{Y}^+ and \mathbf{Y}^- [Eqs. (4) and (5)].
2. Compute the SVD of \mathbf{Y}^- and form $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ [Eq. (8)].
3. Compute the eigenvalues of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ and the associated eigenvectors.

Previously published versions of DMD for estimating time eigenvalues [4] required a fixed-sized time step to generate the data matrices. This algorithm does not have this constraint, though it does require the use of the backward Euler method. Other time discretization methods are possible, but would modify the algorithm. The ability to handle variable-sized time steps is a significant advance because, for problems where delayed neutrons are significant, estimating both the prompt and delayed modes of the system would require very small time steps to resolve the prompt scales and a large number of these steps to integrate to times when delayed neutrons are significant, as we demonstrate below.

The algorithm has flexibility in that the initial condition for the time-dependent calculation can be chosen based on the needs of the analyst. For example, to model an experiment and extract the important eigenmodes, one would initialize the problem with the appropriate experimental initial condition. On the other hand, to compute the dominant eigenmodes in a system, one could use a random initial condition to assure that all of the modes are excited in the system.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. Infinite Medium Problem with Delayed Neutrons

To demonstrate the need for a variable time step method, we consider the neutron flux solution of a twelve group problem with six delayed neutron precursor groups and a spherical buckling approximation for the leakage. This problem results in a transport operator that is an 18×18 matrix for which we can use numerical linear algebra software to estimate the eigenvalues. A subcritical and delayed supercritical case are considered by modifying the radius of the sphere in the buckling. The numerical solution is computed using backward Euler time discretization, and logarithmically-spaced timesteps are used.

The systems considered had a radius of 11.7335 cm for the subcritical case and a radius of 11.735 cm for the supercritical case. These unsteady problems were initialized with a single neutron per cm^3 in the highest energy group at time zero (to approximate probing the system with a fast-neutron source), and used a logarithmically spaced time grid to a final time of $10^{3.55} \approx 3548$ s, using 400 time steps; the first time step is of size $\Delta t = 10^{-11}$ s. A challenge of using the traditional DMD algorithm to analyze these kinds

of problems lies in the very different time scales over which the features of the system manifest. As an example, the prompt multiplication peak occurs around ten nanoseconds into the problem, while the delayed multiplication continues until well into the hundreds of seconds. This is most evident in Fig. 2, where the supercritical behavior of the system is not evident until over one hundred seconds into the evolution of the problem.

Figure 1: Solution in terms of the number density of neutrons, $n(t)$, for the subcritical sphere problem. The black line plots the analytical solution, and the red line plots the backward Euler solution. Vertical blue lines are negative eigenperiods, the inverse of negative α eigenvalues.

Figure 2: Solution in terms of the number density of neutrons, $n(t)$, for the delayed supercritical sphere problem. The labeling is the identical to Figure 1 with the addition of a vertical red line to denote the positive eigenperiod.

Figures 1 and 2 plot the neutron population in the sphere over time. Resolving the early and late time features of this delayed subcritical system would be extremely expensive using a uniform timestep, the present example uses just 400 time points. In these figures the black line corresponds to the exact solution, and the red dashed line is the backward Euler solution. The vertical blue lines correspond to the magnitude of the periods of the exact eigenvalues ($|\alpha|^{-1}$), where blue and red colors respectively indicate negative and positive value. These exact eigenvalues, along with the V-DMD eigenvalues and the per cent mille (pcm) difference between them are tabulated for both the subcritical and supercritical cases in Table I. In the table we can see that for all 18 eigenvalues the V-DMD estimates are within 1 pcm of the reference.

Table I: V-DMD Eigenvalues for Subcritical and Delayed Supercritical Spheres

Subcritical			Supercritical		
V-DMD	Reference	Rel. Diff. (pcm)	V-DMD	Reference	Rel. Diff. (pcm)
-1.67621×10^9	-1.67621×10^9	4.50832×10^{-6}	-1.67597×10^9	-1.67597×10^9	3.39495×10^{-6}
-1.46266×10^9	-1.46266×10^9	1.21889×10^{-5}	-1.46245×10^9	-1.46245×10^9	9.12187×10^{-6}
-1.17322×10^9	-1.17322×10^9	1.33111×10^{-5}	-1.17306×10^9	-1.17306×10^9	1.01906×10^{-5}
-7.9423×10^8	-7.9423×10^8	1.02751×10^{-5}	-7.94119×10^8	-7.94119×10^8	7.6927×10^{-6}
-4.99878×10^8	-4.99878×10^8	9.59993×10^{-6}	-4.99804×10^8	-4.99804×10^8	6.32766×10^{-6}
-2.92659×10^8	-2.92659×10^8	8.25379×10^{-6}	-2.92606×10^8	-2.92606×10^8	5.49621×10^{-6}
-1.66397×10^8	-1.66397×10^8	7.86181×10^{-6}	-1.66365×10^8	-1.66365×10^8	5.5453×10^{-6}
-9.36139×10^7	-9.36139×10^7	7.83863×10^{-6}	-9.35967×10^7	-9.35967×10^7	5.61693×10^{-6}
-5.28136×10^7	-5.28136×10^7	8.18976×10^{-6}	-5.28057×10^7	-5.28057×10^7	5.59484×10^{-6}
-3.3247×10^7	-3.3247×10^7	7.7474×10^{-6}	-3.32436×10^7	-3.32436×10^7	7.96339×10^{-6}
-2.64094×10^7	-2.64094×10^7	6.41958×10^{-5}	-2.64085×10^7	-2.64085×10^7	4.02185×10^{-5}
-609650	-609650	1.01244×10^{-7}	-540139	-540139	1.2533×10^{-7}
-2.6143	-2.6143	0.00692918	-2.60143	-2.60143	0.000432976
-0.743523	-0.743522	0.032869	-0.732142	-0.732142	0.00204506
-0.196728	-0.196729	0.11221	-0.187957	-0.187957	0.0073383
-0.0766106	-0.0766105	0.178187	-0.0699507	-0.0699507	0.0126469
-0.0158091	-0.0158092	0.273722	-0.0149391	-0.0149391	0.0130459
-0.00467554	-0.00467553	0.269541	0.00441678	0.00441678	0.00401589

4. Modak and Gupta Problem

To demonstrate that V-DMD is also applicable to transport problems, and to compare it with the original DMD formulation, we consider a transport problem first published by Modak and Gupta [10] with semi-analytic results published by Kornreich and Parsons [11]. Unlike the infinite medium problem, the exact time evolution operator cannot be explicitly formed. The problem is defined as a 10 mean-free-path, non-multiplying slab of two materials, with $\Sigma_S = 10$ in one material and $\Sigma_S = 9$ in the other. The other nuclear properties are defined as $\Sigma_T = 10$, $\nu\Sigma_f = 0$, and $\chi = 0$. The grain size is varied for separate runs of this simulation, this parameter defines the fraction of the overall length that each slice of material is, compared to the whole. These material slices are arranged in alternating order. The zero grain size case indicates a homogeneous material with average properties.

Previous work has demonstrated that to accurately estimate eigenvalues on these problems, high resolution in space and angle is necessary. The Modak and Gupta problem was solved with V-DMD using a S_{196} discrete ordinates approach with 1000 spatial grid points and 101 logarithmically spaced time steps with the first time step ending at $t = 10^{-5}$ and the last ending at $t = 100$; results using the original, equi-spaced time step formulation of DMD used 101 equally spaced time steps over a time range of 100 using the same

spatial and angular discretizations.

The results of a prior numerical alpha eigenvalue determination is compared against the new V-DMD algorithm and the existing DMD algorithm. The problem is initialized with a random initial condition for the angular flux in all angles and all positions sampled uniformly between zero and one, to ensure that all eigenmodes are excited. The four largest real eigenvalues from these numerical experiments are tabulated in Table II. Bold numbers indicate an agreement for the number in that decimal place with the published results [11]. From the table we notice that V-DMD and DMD have nearly identical performance in the number of digits matched with the semi-analytic results. This demonstrates that we have not sacrificed accuracy in formulating a variable step version of DMD.

Table II: Computed eigenvalues for the Modak and Gupta problem using V-DMD and DMD compared with the semi-analytic results.

Grain Size	Semi-Analytic	V-DMD	DMD
0.5	-0.551429	-0.550814	-0.550814
	-1.71149	-1.70646	-1.70645
	-2.94399	-2.94235	-2.94235
	-5.28234	-5.16961	-5.17338
0.25	-0.703578	-0.704010	-0.704010
	-1.45315	-1.45044	-1.45044
	-3.07282	-3.07073	-3.07073
	-5.26925	-5.15114	-5.15081
0.1	-0.749672	-0.749256	-0.749255
	-1.56062	-1.55665	-1.55665
	-2.96323	-2.96002	-2.96002
	-5.18772	-5.09398	-5.11195
0.05	-0.758893	-0.757022	-0.757022
	-1.56062	-1.56447	-1.56447
	-2.97899	-2.97842	-2.97842
	-5.21764	-5.10019	-5.10619
0	-0.763507	-0.763508	-0.763508
	-1.57201	-1.57201	-1.57202
	-2.98348	-2.98352	-2.98352
	-5.10866	-5.13648	-5.47278

5. CONCLUSIONS

V-DMD is capable of determining time eigenvalues of the neutron transport operator as effectively as DMD. For the infinite medium problem with multiple time scales V-DMD method was able to accurately determine all eigenvalues of the system without requiring the constant time-step size of DMD. We believe that this method will be useful to analyze systems where time-dependent phenomena are important and a range of time scales is also present.

The V-DMD approach is naturally suited to adaptive time stepping methods, and demonstrating its efficacy on such algorithms including non-backward Euler time integration should be explored in future work. Moreover, V-DMD, as well as DMD, should be explored in multiphysics problems, where DMD and V-DMD can be used to estimate evolving modes that do not exactly correspond to α eigenvalues. Work in this

direct has been reported by [12]. The V-DMD approach should enable further analysis of these systems.

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